

Adducts of 4-t-Butylphenoxo Complexes of Oxovanadium(v) with 2-, 3- and 4-Cyanopyridines

K. C. MALHOTRA, BRIJ BALA, NEERAJ SHARMA, S. S. BHATT and S. C. CHAUDHRY*

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

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4-t-Butylphenoxo-complexes of oxovanadium(v) of composition $\text{VOCl}_{3-x}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_x$, where $x = 1 \rightarrow 3$, react with 2-, 3- and 4-cyanopyridines to give adducts of varying composition. 2-Cyanopyridine forms adduct of 1 : 1 composition, coordinating simultaneously through pyridine as well as nitrile nitrogens of the ligand, while 3- and 4-cyanopyridines forms adducts of 1 : 2 composition (metal : ligand) coordinating through only pyridine nitrogen of the ligand.

Compared to a voluminous documentation on the coordination chemistry of cyanopyridines¹⁻⁶, having two potential donor sites, viz. the nitrile group and the pyridine group with metal ions, no attempt seems to have been made on the investigation of coordinating tendency of these ligands towards metal aryloxides. As a part of our ongoing research programme aimed at the synthesis of new aryloxides of oxovanadium(v) and their reactivity⁷ and in view of the well-known relative ability of the cyanopyridines to form adducts showing different modes of coordination, we were prompted to isolate the adducts of 4-t-butylphenoxo-complexes $[\text{VOCl}_{3-x}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_x]$ with 2-, 3- and 4-cyanopyridines. An emphasis has mainly been laid upon the mode of bonding of pyridines to vanadium and the effect of donor ability of the ligands on the nature of V=O bond of the aryloxides.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of 4-t-butylphenoxo-complexes of oxovanadium(v) of composition $\text{VOCl}_{3-x}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_x$, where $x = 1 \rightarrow 3$ in methanol with 2-cyanopyridine in the same solvent lead to the formation of compound of 1 : 1 composition while with 3- and 4-cyanopyridines compounds of 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) composition are formed. The differential behavior of 2-cyanopyridine in forming compounds of different composition compared to other two cyanopyridines has been observed earlier also in its adducts with titanium(IV) halides, zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) salts⁸. Further, it is of interest to mention that no evidence could be obtained concerning the formation of a new ligand *O*-methylpyridine-2-carboximide by the reaction of 2-cyanopyridine with methanol used as a solvent in the reaction unlike the earlier reports⁹. Our observations thus parallel the reports of adduct forming ability of 2-cyanopyridine with nickel(II), palladium(II) and platinum(II) halides¹⁰ and with copper(I), silver(I) and gold(I) perchlorates¹¹, wherein also no evidence for any such metal-promoted reactions was found.

Stoichiometric composition of the molecular adducts has been established by elemental analysis (Table 1). These adducts are hygroscopic, readily soluble in methanol, sparingly soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene

and insoluble in petroleum ether and ether. Insolubility of these adducts in common organic solvents and molten camphor and biphenyl rendered their molecular weight determination impossible. The molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in methanol are quite low (20–25 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) compared to 1 : 1 electrolytes¹², suggesting their non-ionic nature in this solvent.

The ir spectra of 3- and 4-cyanopyridine adducts exhibited bands around 2225 and 2245 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) indicating either no change or insignificant changes in the nitrile stretching modes of these adducts as compared to that of the free bases (2225 and 2240 cm^{-1}). This suggests that the cyano group of these pyridine does not participate in coordination. Instead, the frequencies of the four principal bands of cyanopyridines in the region 1580–1410 cm^{-1} arising from $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bonds experience significant positive shifts in their addition compounds which is in line with the earlier observations of pyridine complexes¹³. Apart from this, the two lower frequency bands at 960–1082 cm^{-1} in free bases appear at higher frequencies on adduct formation. These observations thus suggest the coordination of 3- and 4-cyanopyridines to vanadium through ring nitrogen as reported earlier^{9,11-13}.

In the ir spectra of 2-cyanopyridine adducts, however, the band present at 2235 cm^{-1} (CN) in the free bases experiences a positive shift by about 35–65 cm^{-1} on complexation. Besides, the characteristic bands at 1400–1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) of pure 2-cyanopyridine also shift significantly to higher wave numbers thus suggesting simultaneously coordination through nitrogens of both nitrile as well as pyridine ring nitrogens to the vanadium metal. Had there been coordination from these sites to two different vanadium atoms as has been reported in the case of ruthenium(II) cyclopentadienyl complexes¹⁴, there would have been a decrease in the position of ν_{CN} relative to that observed in the free ligand. Moreover in that case, the stoichiometry of the adduct would have been 2 : 1 (vanadium : ligand). In the present case, however, the stoichiometric composition of 2-cyanopyridine adducts has been found to be 1 : 1 (Table 1). Thus the characteristic positive shift of the bands of both $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and nitrile group of 2-cyanopyridine coupled with 1 : 1

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF 2-, 3- AND 4-CYANOPYRIDINE ADDUCTS OF $[\text{VOCl}_{3-x}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_x]$

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found / (Calcd.)		VC=N	VV=O	VV-O	VV-Cl	VV-N
		V	Cl					
$[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{-CNpy}]$	Brown	12.9(13.0)	17.9(18.1)	2280	935	770	480, 535	350
$[\text{VOCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{-CNpy}]$	Brown	10.2(10.0)	7.0(7.0)	2290	960	760	540	352
$[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_3\cdot 2\text{-CNpy}]$	Black	7.9(8.2)	—	2300	970	680	—	355
$[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})\cdot (3\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Brown	10.1(10.3)	14.1(14.3)	2225	935	775	485, 530	325
$[\text{VOCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot (3\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Brown	7.9(8.4)	5.5(5.8)	2225	965	758	545	345
$[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_3\cdot (3\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Black	6.7(7.0)	—	2220	980	685	—	348
$[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})\cdot (4\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Brown	10.1(10.3)	13.9(14.3)	2245	928	775	478, 538	330
$[\text{VOCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot (4\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Black	7.3(8.4)	6.4(5.8)	2245	958	678	542	332
$[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_3\cdot (4\text{-CNpy})_2]$	Black	7.5(7.0)	—	2240	978	672	—	335

stoichiometric composition of its adducts with oxovanadium aryloxides, confirms the bidentate nature of this ligand leading to the formation of 6-coordinate adducts. Apparently electronic factor seems to play a dominating role compared to steric factor arising from the inaccessibility of the electron pair on ring nitrogen for coordination in the complexes under study.

A qualitative information has also been obtained concerning the effects of linkage of pyridines on the nature of V=O bond and new V-N bonds formed. On comparing the parent complexes $\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})$, $\text{VOCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2$ and $\text{VO}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_3$ with the adducts, one observes that the adducts show the V=O band displaced to lower region by 60–70 cm^{-1} from that observed at 980, 1008 and 1020 cm^{-1} in the respective complexes. This decrease in $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ stretch may be attributed to a strong bonding between the donor nitrogen atom of cyanopyridines and vanadium. In general, the greater the basicity of the ligands, the lower is the frequency of V=O vibration. Similar explanation has been offered earlier^{15,16} also for uranyl and vanadium complexes respectively. The ir spectra of the adducts have exhibited bands in the region 320–360 cm^{-1} , assigned to the (V–N_{base}) bond¹⁷. The bands due to V–O_{phenoxo} and C–O–V vibrations have been observed to move to higher frequencies in the adducts relative to that in the parent complexes. The reason for this increase may be attributed to the strengthening of the phenoxovanadium bond with the introduction of the base in accordance with earlier observations¹⁸.

The DTA/TGA curves of the adducts $[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})\cdot (4\text{CNpy})_2]$ ^(I) and $[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})\cdot (2\text{CNpy})]$ ^(II) in air (Figs. 1 and 2) have indicated them to be stable upto ~60° and begin to loose weight at 65°. The decomposition seems to proceed in two stages. An initial weight-loss of 41.47 and 26.88% for the respective complexes in the first stage corresponds to the removal of coordinated cyanopyridine ligands (i.e. loss of two 4-CNpy ligands in (I) and of one 2-CNpy in (II)) yielding $\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})$ as an intermediate. The subsequent weight-losses of 36.36% for (I) and 46.54% for (II) in the second stage may be proposed to be due to the oxidative decomposition of intermediate to yield V_2O_5 at 500° as the ultimate product.

Fig. 2. Thermograms of $\text{VOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})\cdot 2(2\text{-CNpy})$.

This overall decomposition can be rationalised in terms of the reactions,

The vanadium content in the residue has been found to be consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the adducts. The entire decomposition of the adducts reveals two exothermic peaks with maxima at 203.8 and 475° for (I) and 257.3 and 484.3° for (II), attributed to the oxidative decomposition in the DTA curve.

Experimental

Oxovanadium(v)-4-t-butylphenoxides of composition $\text{VOCl}_{3-x}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_x$, $x = 1 \rightarrow 3$, were synthesized by the method reported earlier⁷. The 2-, 3- and 4-cyanopyridines (Aldrich) were recrystallized from ethanol and the purity was checked by m.p. and ir spectral data. Vanadium was estimated gravimetrically as V_2O_5 while chlorine by Volhard's method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR 4250 spectrophotometer. Thermograms were recorded on a Shimadzu DT-40 analyser, while conductivity was measured on an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge using 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in methanol.

Cyanopyridine adducts : In a typical reaction, the methanolic solution of 2-, 3- and 4-cyanopyridine were reacted with oxovanadium(v)-4-t-butylphenoxides in 2 : 1 molar ratio in the same solvent under reflux, when a clear solution was obtained. The resulting solution was then concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid compounds that separated by the addition of petroleum ether were dried under reduced pressure.

In case of the adducts of 2-cyanopyridine with oxovanadium(v)-4-t-butylphenoxides, the reaction was carried out in benzene also. The adducts isolated were identical to those obtained in methanol, thus excluding the possibility of any metal-promoted reaction between 2-cyanopyridine and methanol as reported earlier⁹.

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